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**Determinants of Childhood Malnutrition in Rwanda:
A Distributional Regression Approach**

vorgelegt von

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Abstract

This thesis aims to determine the causes of chronic malnutrition in children between the ages of 0 and 59 months in Rwanda. Specifically, factors affecting the stunting z-score, a measure of deviance from the WHO reference growth curve values of height at a certain age, are ascertained. A number of variables from the dataset of the 2019-20 DHS survey in Rwanda are extracted and incorporated into several distributional regression models based on the the Generalized Additive Model for Location, Scale and Shape (GAMLSS) framework. After explaining the workings of GAMLSS, a comprehensive variable and model selection is conducted yielding a final model based on Johnson's S_u distribution. The results of the analysis confirm most of the findings of prior studies conducted in different parts of the world. In conclusion, prioritized policy recommendations based on the final model are mapped out in order to alleviate the widespread issue of childhood stunting in Rwanda and soften its consequences for Rwanda's humanitarian and economic future. Further areas of research and additional ways to refine the model, which lie out of the scope of this thesis, are proposed. These include methodical approaches such as *gamboostLSS*, cross validation and adjusting for the survey design, as well as model adjustments, such as splitting the sample population into 3 different age groups with different nutritional needs.

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1 Introduction

Zero hunger is listed as one of the primary goals of the United Nations' 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (United Nations General Assembly, 2015). According to its 2023 special report, more than 600 million people world wide are expected to suffer from hunger and malnutrition in 2030, the largest population share being affected in Africa (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2023). The causes of this are manifold and include, among others, climate change, armed conflicts and the COVID-19 pandemic (FAO et al., 2023).

The sub-saharan country of Rwanda is exceptional in many regards: unlike many of its neighboring countries, Rwanda has seen an almost meteoric economic rise in terms of GDP growth (World Bank, 2024). Listed as one of the most favorable countries to do business in according to the Ease of Doing Business Index 2019 (World Bank, 2019), which, among others, takes things such as getting credit, registering property, receiving construction permits and resolving insolvency, into account, it is easily called an economic powerhouse.

In his State of the Nation Address in December 2015, the Rwandan president Paul Kagame, who's been ruling the country since April 22nd, 2000, published his "Vision 2050": a number of socio-economic, legal, environmental and infrastructure-related measures to be undertaken which are supposed to lift the country and its inhabitants out of poverty and make Rwanda a global player on the stage of international trade (The Republic of Rwanda, 2020). Rwanda's capital city Kigali boasts a 300 million USD convention center containing a luxury 5 star hotel intended to cater to an international audience of investors and entrepreneurs (Himbara, 2018) and a government-subsidized airline "RwandAir" which features non-stop flights to international hubs like London, Paris and Dubai (flightconnections.com, 2024). Kagame even goes so far as to call Rwanda the "Singapore of Africa" (Caryl, 2015): a small country that rose from poverty to its position as a wealthy international business hub.

But once you start peeling back the layers of government-published figures (NISR, 2023), staged photos of conferences (Rwandan Ministry of Foreign Affairs and International Cooperation, 2019) and outright propaganda measures (Greenberg, 2018), a more sinister reality emerges — one that affects the most vulnerable

members of any society: its children. While life as an adult in Rwanda can be hard, the fates of many children in Rwanda are even more bleak. As Human Rights Watch reported in 2006¹, 2015² and again in 2020³, the Rwandan police in Kigali specifically targets so called 'undesirables', that is poor, unaccompanied mothers, street vendors, beggar children, sex workers and anyone deemed a potential eyesore towards international visitors, rounding them up and locking them away in a prison off the city limits. In addition to its many human rights abuses, approximately 33% of the country's children suffer from chronic undernutrition. This leads to the question whether the country's "Vision 2050" can realistically be achieved, and whether achieving these goals is sustainable if the country's literal future is severely endangered.

The aim of this thesis is to determine and quantify the main determinants of chronic underdevelopment of children aged 0 to 59 months in Rwanda. This is done via a distributional regression approach, the Generalized Additive Model for Location, Scale and Shape (GAMLSS). This class of regression models allows for greater flexibility than a standard linear regression and is exceptionally useful when one is interested in modeling the more extreme quantiles of a distribution and asserting risk factors that contribute towards childhood malnutrition which might otherwise be lost.

In the following section we will first focus on the source and method of collection of the data this analysis builds on. We'll highlight a number of insights from the accompanying final report and point out what we know and what we don't yet know when it comes to childhood malnutrition in Rwanda. The term "z-score" as a measure of chronic undernutrition is introduced and we will show the benefits of using this measure over other ways to evaluate the developmental status of a child.

A closer inspection of the data will be undertaken in Section 2 and we will point out why this necessitates the need for a more complex class of regression models and where the use of standard regression models falls short. Section 4 will describe the mathematical and statistical workings of GAMLSS itself and apply this method to the data. Section 5 concludes our analysis and gives an outlook into potential areas of future research and additional extensions to our model.

¹Human Rights Watch, 2006.

²Mudge, 2015.

³Human Rights Watch, 2020.

2 Data Source and Characteristics

This thesis builds on a dataset acquired from the Demographic and Health Survey (DHS) Program. The DHS Program is an initiative funded by the United States Agency for International Development (USAID) and collects survey data on the demographic, health-related and nutritional conditions of the populations of over 90 countries (The DHS Program, 2024). The dataset at hand stems from the 2019-20 DHS survey conducted in Rwanda in cooperation with the National Institute of Statistics of Rwanda (NISR) and the Rwandan Ministry of Health (MOH). It encompasses a trove of data on the environmental, familial, housing and health conditions of 55920 individuals, 8092 of these are children between the ages of 0 and 59 months. Due to the vast amount of information available, a careful variable selection, as well as some data cleaning and simplification steps were conducted; more on this in Sections 3.1, 3.2 and 4.3.

2.1 Survey Design

In order to gather representative data, the survey was conducted via a 2-step cluster sampling procedure. This is done to ensure that marginalized population groups, such as very rich people or people living in lesser populated or rural areas of the country are appropriately represented.

In step 1, the country of Rwanda was split into 5 different provinces, namely the area in and around the capital city of Kigali, the Northern, Eastern, Western and Southern provinces. This is done in accordance with the 2012 Rwanda Housing and Population Census (NISR et al., 2021, pp. 353–). These 5 provinces were again divided into districts, then into sectors, which in turn were divided into *clusters*, which can represent single villages or collections of villages, neighborhoods of small cities or blocks of large cities. This division into clusters is based on the population density. Clusters themselves consist of individual *Households*. The clusters are then stratified with respect to urban or rural geography and a list of all households in every cluster is made, so that subgroups of the population are adequately represented. The number of clusters to be selected for the 2020-21 DHS survey was set to 500 with 26 households to be interviewed per cluster. The probability of picking

an individual cluster is proportional to its population size: urban areas with a high population density are therefore more likely to be picked than their rural counterparts. This is done to ensure that the sample is more representative of the overall population.

In step 2, 26 households from every cluster were randomly picked to be interviewed and the interviews conducted.

This survey design leads to cluster and stratification issues, as the people interviewed within the context of the survey are no longer part of a random sample. If the survey design was not conducted, however, and one were to gather data proportional to the number of people of specific subgroups or areas, this could lead to a sample size that is too small to properly be statistically interpreted (e.g. just 10 people from an area representing 1% of the population when the overall target sample size is set to 1000 people). While an increase in the overall number of individuals surveyed seems like a good approach to mitigate these effects, such a strategy can lead to a number of unwanted side-effects.

Budget or time constraints may limit the sample size that can reasonably be collected. And even if the budget is of little concern, a large sample size may incur issues in terms of data quality, caused by things such as interviewer fatigue due to working on the same project for a prolonged period of time. Mitigating these issues via an increase in the number of interviewers necessitates additional schooling sessions and may lead to quality concerns in the individual interviewer's performance or their field supervision. When conducting their surveys the DHS Program tries to find a balance between budget constraints and data quality concerns (The DHS Program, 2014).

When performing a standard regression analysis, the bias introduced due to the survey design can be mitigated via packages in statistical software, but no such packages are available for the GAMLSS framework used in this thesis. Manually adjusting for the survey design lies outside of the scope of this treatise, so the data will henceforth be considered as originating from a random sample of the population.

2.2 The Stunting Z-Score

Childhood malnutrition can be expressed via different metrics, not all of which are an appropriate choice for an analysis like the one at hand. Therefore, this section will briefly explain the differences between the 3 most common measures of undernutrition in children and point out why stunting is the best metric to be used.

Underweight is measured via the individual child’s weight for its age. A child that is underweight weighs too little compared to other children of the same age. Underweight represents a combination of both long-term (too little height-for-age) and short-term (too little weight-for-height) malnutrition.

Wasting measures the weight-for-height of a child. A child that is wasted is too thin for its height. The causes of this can be attributed to disease or an acute lack of proper nutrition.

Stunting describes the condition of a child that is too short for its age and is a measure of chronic undernutrition. A child that receives too little nutrients over a longer span of time will not grow as much as well nourished children of the same age.

This analysis will model the stunting z -score as the target variable in order to quantify possible determinants of stunting. Victora et al. (2008) note that a child’s height at 2 years old is the best predictor of the potential economic and productive capacity of individuals, further underlining the choice of the stunting z -score as the target variable in this analysis.

The z -score modeled in this analysis is the distance from the median height in standard deviations as defined in the WHO growth reference chart. As can be seen from Figures A.1 and A.2 in the Appendix, the variance of the reference growth curve increases over time. This necessitates the use of a standardized z -score, defined as

$$Z_i = \frac{AC_i - m}{s}, \quad (2.1)$$

where AC_i is the child’s height in centimeters, m is the reference population median height value and s is an estimate of the standard deviation calculated with respect to age, gender and a number of other characteristics (Fenske et al., 2011, Stasinopoulos et al., 2024, pp. 239-240). The reference data stems from a 2006 WHO report that, among others, calculates reference height-for-age values based on 27334 measurements of children between the ages of 0 and 60 months from 6 different regions on Earth (WHO, 2006).

2.3 Insights and Limitations of the DHS Final Report

Accompanying the dataset is a 619 page final report that summarizes some of the most important information gathered via the survey (NISR et al., 2021). In Chapter

11 an assessment concerning the nutritional profile of children is conducted. The report concludes that approximately one third of all Rwandan children between the ages of 6 and 59 months suffer from a body length that is too low for their age. There seems to be a strong negative correlation between the stunting score and the education of a child's mother: a higher education leads to a drastically reduced risk of stunting (of all children under the age of 5 that were determined to be stunted, 45% had mothers without any formal education, while only 6% of the children of mothers with a greater than secondary education (those who received more than 12 of formal education in Rwanda) were classified as stunted).

Furthermore, it is determined that older children (e.g. those between the ages of 24 and 35 months) are at a much higher risk of being stunted compared to children less than 6 months old (40% vs 16%). Children of wealthier households are much less frequently faced with stunting: only 11% of the children of the wealthiest 20% of all households are classified as stunted, while children from the poorest 20% face stunting at an average rate of 49%. A similar trend can be detected when observing the average stunting percentages in 5 different geographical regions of Rwanda. Children living in the Western or Northern Region of Rwanda are stunted at a rate of 40% and 41%, while on average only 29% and 33% of children living in the East or the South of the country are stunted. The lowest stunting rate can be observed in the region in and around Kigali where 21% of all children are stunted. In addition, the report states that just 22% of all children between the ages of 6 and 23 months had their nutritional requirements in terms of food diversity and meal frequency met (this classification adheres to the 2021 WHO and UNICEF guidelines on infant and young child feeding practices, see UNICEF and WHO, 2021).

What the reports lacks, however, is clear information on which of these factors contribute the most to the stunting risk and whether there are any other factors that have not been considered. The aim of this thesis is to answer these questions and identify the most important factors contributing towards stunting in children. Based on these results, policy recommendations will be developed in order to point out ways to alleviate the stunting crisis in Rwanda.

3 Exploratory Data Analysis

3.1 Preliminary Variable Selection

The first 5 years of a child’s life are considered one of the most important periods of development (Shonkoff et al., 2000). Brain development occurs at an unprecedented rate and vital motor, cognitive and social skills are acquired during this period. A lack of nutrients and proper nutrition can lead to disastrous consequences for a child and its future, such as severe health issues, permanent cognitive deficiencies and as a consequence a much reduced income and economic standing (Victora et al., 2008). According to Bello and Ijaiya (1998), improper nutrition may even lead to mental damage inhibiting a child’s ability to pay attention in class and reduce their productivity after school, further exacerbating this issue. In fact, Martorell and Zongrone (2012) establish that malnutrition has inter-generational effects even if the socio-economic situation of a formerly malnourished mother has improved. This is because, among others, socio-cultural (fear of giving birth to a large baby and therefore limiting the intake of food during pregnancy) and physiological effects (such as insufficient uterine, pelvic or placental sizes) come into play. It is for these reasons that the United Nations as well as the DHS program pay special attention to this critical period of a child’s life and gather data on this subset of the population.

While the determinants of childhood malnutrition are manifold, a number of recurrent socio-economic, environmental and nutritional causes of this global crisis have been identified. Katoch (2022) summarizes the results of 37 studies focusing on the causes of malnutrition in children in developing countries, such as India, Ethiopia, Bangladesh, Ghana and others. Among the most frequent are the mother’s education, the economic standing of the household, the availability of sanitation facilities (including stool disposal and clean water access), as well as breastfeeding practices, maternal anemia (lack of hemoglobin in the mother’s blood which transports oxygen to cells), the child’s birth weight and its gender. The dataset provided by the DHS Program contains information on all of these and many more factors. Table 3.1 provides an overview of the preliminary variables extracted from the dataset at hand.

Covariate	Description	Studies supporting choice
age_months	Child's age in months	Hien and Hoa (2009); Demissie and Worku (2013)
BORD	Child's birth order number	Fenske et al. (2011)
B0	Whether child is a twin	Fenske et al. (2011)
B4	Sex of child	Wells (2000)
HW57	Anemia level (child)	Mohammed et al. (2019); Lozoff et al. (2006)
V457	Anemia level (mother)	Nadhiroh et al. (2023)
M14	Number of antenatal visits during pregnancy	Forero-Ramirez et al. (2014)
V012	Respondent's current age (mother)	Adedokun and Yaya (2021)
V133	Education in single years (mother)	Adedokun and Yaya (2021), among others
child_deaths	Whether the woman had any children who died	Wright et al. (2021)
HV009	Number of household members	Wahyuni et al. (2023)
HV014	Number of children 5 and under (de jure)	Kumari (2007); Wong et al. (2014)
V102	Type of residence (rural / urban)	NISR et al. (2021); Menon et al. (2000)
V190	Wealth quintile	Striessnig and Bora (2020), among others

Table 3.1: Preliminary selection of variables either extracted from or computed based on information from the dataset. Exemplary studies or papers indicating the potential relevance of each covariate are listed.

A more detailed explanation as to why these specific factors were chosen as regressors will be presented in the upcoming sections. The variables are grouped into a total of 3 categories: physiological attributes (anything directly relating to the child's body), maternal conditions (factors relating to the child's mother) and household and environmental determinants affecting the living situation of the individual families.

3.1.1 Physiological Attributes

As described in Section 2.2, the stunting z-score is an appropriate way to measure chronic undernutrition in children. This analysis will consider the child's age in months (`age_months`), as Hien and Hoa (2009) and Demissie and Worku (2013), among others, have found that older children face an increased risk in becoming stunted. Fenske et al. (2011) determined that a child's birth order (the position in which they were born among siblings) has a progressively negative effect on a child's stunting score, with the effect worsening the further down the birth hierarchy the child was born. The variable `BORD` was therefore extracted from the dataset. Additionally, twin births seem to be at greater risk as 2 children compete for the same, limited amount of resources (also Fenske et al., 2011), so this was also considered as a possible determinant (labeled `B0`).

Wells (2000) argues that natural selection causes boys to be more vulnerable to environmental stresses than girls, as an increased infant morbidity in male children maximizes the chances of successful maternal reproduction. This is because weaker

male offspring are less likely to reproduce. The interplay between environmental stressors, such as poor nutrient availability, and susceptibility to disease in early life might result in lower z-scores for boys. The variable B4 indicating the child's sex was therefore extracted from the dataset. Lastly, Mohammed et al. (2019) found a link between stunting and anemia in children. Anemia has been shown to have severe, long-lasting health consequences, such as diminished motor and cognitive development or behavioral issues (Lozoff et al., 2006). The individual child's anemia level is therefore considered as a covariate (HW57).

3.1.2 Maternal Conditions

Nadhiroh et al. (2023) emphasize that stunting may be linked to the prevalence of maternal anemia. V457 categorizes women into 4 different anemia categories, namely `not anemic`, `mild`, `moderate` and `severe`, depending on their hemoglobin levels measured in grams per 100ml of blood. Forero-Ramirez et al. (2014) found a weak indication that prenatal care might be positively correlated with a decrease in stunting, so the number of antenatal visits during pregnancy (M14) is also included in this analysis. While there is no specific information on the level of quality of the prenatal care available to the surveyed women, the DHS final report (NISR et al., 2021, p. 132) states that 97.7% of the mothers who gave birth during the last 5 years preceding the study had access to professional prenatal care, either provided by a doctor (4.5%), nurse (92.9%) or another, schooled health care specialist (0.3%). Adedokun and Yaya (2021) found evidence that children of mothers aged 15 to 24 years are at higher risk of suffering from malnutrition than children of mothers aged 25 and older. Therefore the mother's age (V012) was also considered as a covariate.

Many studies link a mother's education to the well-being of her children. A higher level of education is associated with a decrease in the risk of stunting, as a better education allows mothers to seek higher paying jobs. Mothers are therefore more able to provide adequate food and medical care to their children (see, for example, Adedokun and Yaya, 2021 and Burchi, 2012). While Rwanda has a free and compulsory 9-year school attendance law since 2006 (Rwandan Ministry of Education, 2006), there's stark differences between the individual mother's educational attainments. The number of years of education a child's mother has received (V133) is therefore included in the analysis as a numeric covariate.

While child mortality in Rwanda has consistently become lower and lower over the last 30+ years, approximately 1 in 22 children in Rwanda die before their 5th birthday (NISR et al., 2021). The main causes of childhood mortality are infectious diseases such as pneumonia, diarrhoea or malaria, as well as birth complications

among newborns (WHO, 2024). Wright et al. (2021) find a strong link between stunting and childhood mortality; hence, information on whether a mother has had any children die was included in the analysis as a binary variable, `child_deaths`.

3.1.3 Household and Environmental Determinants

The family size (e.g. the total number of household members aged 5 and above) as well as the number of siblings aged 59 months and under were also added as covariates (`HV009` and `HV014` respectively). Wahyuni et al. (2023) links an increase in the stunting risk in toddlers with an increase in the number of overall family members. Kumari (2007) observed a negative correlation between an increase in the number of children in a family and every individual child’s nutritional status. Wong et al. (2014) confirm this observation.

The family’s type of residence (rural or urban) might also play a role in affecting a child’s stunting score. Many household characteristics, such as access to electricity, clean water or medical facilities, differ greatly between urban and rural households. Menon et al. (2000) and the results from the DHS final report on Rwanda (NISR et al., 2021) both support adding information about that as a regressor. These characteristics were included as a binary variable (`V102`).

Striessnig and Bora (2020) confirm earlier studies that found a strong link between a household’s wealth and a child’s stunting risk. The DHS survey dataset distinguishes between 5 different wealth categories: poorest, poor, middle, richer and richest. A household’s wealth category is determined through its ownership of a select number of items, such as a television, a radio, a car and residential attributes (such as access to electricity, the type of sanitation facility and drinking water source). The individual presences of all these characteristics are assigned standardized scores which are summed up. All surveyed households are ranked according to this score and then separated into 5 different groups containing the same number of individuals (Croft et al., 2023). `V190` captures this information in regards to every child.

While detailed information about each individual household characteristic and item ownership is present in the dataset, the 5 wealth index categories were added as a single, categorical regressor instead of taking all individual characteristics into account. Otherwise the large amount of information included in the calculation of the wealth index would likely cause multicollinearity issues with other covariates.

3.2 Data Cleaning, Adjustments and Simplifications

3.2.1 Sample Selection Process

As mentioned in the introduction to chapter 2, the dataset at hand consists of 8 databases with information on 55920 individuals living in 12949 households. 8092 of these individuals are children between the ages of 0 and 59 months. Figure 3.1 shows the sample selection process that was conducted.

Not all of the 8092 children were measured, so 4271 observations that did not contain any data on the children’s z-score were excluded. Furthermore, 35 entries in the dataset seemed to have invalid data concerning the total number of children in the household, as defined in HV014. These entries were also removed. Of the remaining 3786 observations 6 entries had invalid height or weight data (HW2 or HW3 were set to *Other*, *Refused* or *Not present*, indicating either unknown reasons for not having measured the child’s height and/or weight, a refusal by the mother to have the child measured or no caretaker being present at the time the measurements were supposed to be taken).

The *Guide to DHS Statistics* (Croft et al., 2023, p. 463) mentions a “plausibility check” that is conducted when processing the raw survey data. Z-scores of above 6 or below -6 standard deviations from the median height-for-age value are marked as *flagged cases*. Out of the remaining 3780 observations, 6 observations were tagged as *flagged cases* which were henceforth deleted. Finally, 373 observations did not contain valid anemia data for either the mother or the child. These observations were also deleted, resulting in the final number of individuals to be considered in this analysis of $n = 3401$ children.

One might also make the case that the father’s or male caretakers education might have an influence on the child’s stunting z-score. According to Burchi (2012), who analyzed data on 6876 children from Mozambique, for each additional year of the father’s education the stunting z-score increased between 0.012 (SD = 0.008) and 0.021 (SD = 0.006). While in the dataset at hand there is information available for the educational attainments of some of these children’s fathers, 584 observations do not contain any such information. This is because either the mother is a single parent raising the child, the father is dead or unknown or could otherwise not be interviewed. In order to keep the sample size as large as possible so that more reliable results can be received, it was refrained from including the father’s or male caretakers years of education in this analysis.

Figure 3.1: Flow chart showing the sample selection process and number of observations removed per step. The final number of observations to be considered in this analysis is $n = 3401$.

3.2.2 Variable Adjustments

Besides selecting the regressors most likely to be relevant, the level of detail of the data at hand raised the need for a number of simplifications to be made. This section details the steps that were undertaken in this regard.

The birth order of every child is listed as a numeric variable. While studies have shown that an increase in the birth order of a child has a negative effect on the child's stunting z-score (see Fenske et al. (2011) and Section 3.1.1 of this thesis), the numeric information saved in `BORD` was simplified into 4 different categories, namely:

- category 1: first born child
- category 2: birth index 2 or 3
- category 3: birth index 4 or 5
- category 4: birth index 6 and higher

This grouping matches that of the DHS Final Report on Rwanda (see, for example NISR et al., 2021, p. 139).

The variables `HW57` and `V457` were both simplified from 4 different categories into binary variables and relabeled `c_anem` and `m_anem`, respectively. If a child or a mother is not or just mildly anemic, this is represented as 0. If a child or a mother is classified as anemic or severely anemic, this is represented as 1. This simplification was made in order to receive more clear results on whether anemia does or does not have an impact on childhood stunting in Rwanda. Prior studies come to differing conclusions: a study conducted by Heesemann et al. (2021) found no connection between anemia and stunting, while Muchie (2016) found a positive correlation between the severity of anemia and a decrease in the stunting z-score.

While the results in Forero-Ramirez et al. (2014) point towards a slight decrease in the stunting risk in children whose mothers received prenatal care, both an inadequate and a very high number of prenatal care visits might be linked to a decrease in a child's stunting score. Therefore, not only the number of prenatal visits during pregnancy is taken into account, but also the number of prenatal visits squared, henceforth referred to as `M14_squared`.

The variable `child_deaths` is itself a simplification from 2 other variables extracted from the DHS dataset, namely `V206` (number of sons who have died) and `V207` (number of daughters who have died). Differentiating between the number of daughters and sons a mother has lost was deemed unnecessary. If a mother has lost

1 or more children of any gender, the variable `child_deaths` is set to 1; otherwise it is set to 0.

Based on the information from HV014 (number of children under 5 in household) the number of siblings of each child ages 5 and under was calculated by subtracting 1 from all entries. This way a child with an entry of HV014 = 1 is indicated to have no siblings aged 5 and under and any value above that indicates a specific number of siblings aged 5 and under. For the sake of simplicity, the resulting number of siblings aged 5 and under is saved under the same label, HV014.

3.2.3 Final List of Covariates

Table 3.2 grants an overview over all covariates that will be considered in the analysis in Chapter 4, along with their types and value ranges or categories.

Covariate	Description	Type	Value range / categories
<code>age_months</code>	Child's age in months	numeric	0 – 59 months
<code>BORD</code>	Birth order number	categorical	1, 2 – 3, 4 – 5, 6+
<code>B0</code>	Child is twin	binary	0 = single birth, 1 = twin birth
<code>B4</code>	Sex of child	binary	0 = female, 1 = male
<code>c_anem</code>	Anemia level (child)	binary	0 = not or mildly anemic, 1 = moderate or severely anemic
<code>m_anem</code>	Anemia level (mother)	binary	0 = not or mildly anemic, 1 = moderate or severely anemic
<code>M14</code>	Number of antenatal visits during pregnancy	numeric	0, . . . , 9 visits
<code>(M14)²</code>	Number of antenatal visits during pregnancy (squared)	numeric	0, . . . , 9 visits
<code>V012</code>	Respondent's current age (mother)	numeric	15, . . . , 49 years
<code>V133</code>	Education in single years (mother)	numeric	0, . . . , 20 years
<code>child_deaths</code>	Whether the woman had any children who died	binary	0 = no kids died, 1 = woman lost at least 1 child
<code>HV009</code>	Number of household members	numeric	2, . . . , 16 people
<code>HV014</code>	Number of siblings 5 and under	numeric	0, . . . , 5 siblings
<code>V102</code>	Type of residence (rural / urban)	binary	0 = rural, 1 = urban
<code>V190</code>	Wealth index combined	categorical	Poorest, poorer, middle, richer or richest quintile

Table 3.2: Final selection of covariates to be considered in the upcoming analysis. This includes the amendments and simplifications made in Section 3.2.2.

3.3 Descriptive Statistics

The total number of individuals to be considered in this analysis is 3401 (see Figure 3.1). A weighted histogram of the data is shown in Figure 3.2. It is apparent that the extracted data is approximately normally distributed and centered around a z-score of -1.5 . A large proportion of children seems to be affected by stunting (z-scores of -2 and below). The tails of the distribution appear a bit heavier than those of a normal distribution, indicating the presence of a significant number of extreme stunting cases (z-scores of -3 and below).

Figure 3.2: Weighted histogram of the stunting z-scores of the $n = 3401$ extracted individuals. The data appears to be approximately normally distributed, although it seems to be slightly right skewed.

3.4 Limitations of Standard Regression Models

While one might initially be poised to perform a standard linear regression on the dataset at hand, there's a number of things limiting the explanatory power and validity of the results of this method. The following sections will first fit a weighted linear regression model to the extracted data, then check whether the residuals of this model are normally distributed and whether they have a constant variance. A violation of these assumptions (namely MLR.5¹ and MLR.6²) invalidate a linear regression model.

¹The variance of the error term \mathbf{u} conditioned on all regressors $\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_K$ is constant: $\text{Var}(\mathbf{u} \mid \mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_K) = \sigma^2$. This is known as *homoscedasticity*. If this condition does not hold, *heteroscedasticity* is present.

²The errors u_i are independent of the regressors $\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_K$ and normally distributed with mean $\mu = 0$ and variance σ^2 : $u_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2) \forall i = 1, 2, \dots, n$

3.4.1 Simplest Approach: Fitting a Weighted Linear Regression Model to the Data

In order to determine which factors might have an influence on the stunting score of Rwandan children, a weighted linear regression model WLR was fitted to the extracted data. As mentioned in Section 2.1, the dataset includes individual weighting factors for every individual in order to remove the bias introduced by the sample design. These individual weighting factors can be included in a standard linear regression model, which was specified as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{HW70}_i = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{age_months}_i + \beta_2 \text{BORD}_i + \beta_3 \text{B0}_i + \beta_4 \text{B4}_i \\ & + \beta_5 \text{HW57}_i + \beta_6 \text{V457}_i + \beta_7 \text{M14}_i + \beta_8 (\text{M14})_i^2 \\ & + \beta_9 \text{V012}_i + \beta_{10} \text{V133}_i + \beta_{11} \text{child_deaths}_i \\ & + \beta_{12} \text{HV009}_i + \beta_{13} \text{HV014}_i + \beta_{14} \text{V102}_i + \beta_{15} \text{V190}_i \end{aligned} \quad (3.1)$$

This weighted linear regression model WLR takes all coefficients into account which were specified in the final list of covariates (see Section 3.2.3). A histogram of the residuals is displayed in Figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3: Histogram and density curve of the residuals of the weighted linear regression model WLR. While the residuals appear to be approximately normally distributed, they are in fact not.

While the histogram suggests that the residuals from the weighted linear regression model WLR are approximately normally distributed, a closer inspection shows that this seems to not actually be the case. Figure 3.4 compares a fitted normal distribution with parameters $\mu = 0$ and $\sigma = 1.0426$ to the density of the residuals produced by the weighted linear regression model. One can clearly see that the 2 distributions differ, especially in the tips and a bit less clearly in the tails. One might also make the point that the density of the residuals from the weighted linear regression model seem to be slightly skewed to the right.

Figure 3.4: Comparison between the density of the residuals of the weighted linear regression model WLR and a fitted normal distribution with parameters $\mu = 0$ and $\sigma = 1.0426$. The chart shows clear differences between the 2 distributions, especially with regards to the tip and the tails.

Additionally, a Shapiro-Wilk test (Shapiro and Wilk, 1965) was conducted on the residuals of the weighted linear regression model. The Shapiro-Wilk test is a commonly used statistical test which is used in order to check whether a data sample stems from a normal distribution. The null hypothesis H_0 states that this is the case, while the alternative hypothesis H_1 states that the data does not originate from a normal distribution.

Running this test yielded a value of the test statistic W of 0.9966 and a p-value much smaller than 0.05 ($5.926 \cdot 10^{-7}$). The Shapiro-Wilk test therefore rejects the null hypothesis that the residuals of the fitted weighted linear regression model are normally distributed at a confidence level of $\alpha = 0.05$. A different regression model might provide a better fit.

3.4.2 Using the Worm Plot as an Additional Diagnostic Device

A worm plot is a graphical diagnostic tool that can be used to assess the goodness of fit of a regression model, especially with respect to the tails (kurtosis) and skewness of the distribution. Originally developed by Buuren and Fredriks (2001) it serves as an alternative way to display the information of a standard Q-Q-plot (quantile-quantile-plot), namely making it easier to identify the deviance of the residuals of a regression model from a theoretical distribution (in this case a standard normal distribution with mean $\mu = 0$ and standard deviation $\sigma = 1$). Figure 3.5 shows a worm plot for the residuals of the fitted weighted linear regression model from Section 3.4.1.

Figure 3.5: Worm plot of the residuals of the weighted linear regression model. 2 observations (numbers 156 and 2912) lie outside of the plotting area at 3.3 and 3.6 standard deviations from the mean and deviation values of 1.3 and 1.95 respectively; these were cut off in order to make the plot more readable.

A worm plot consists of 2 ellipses (displayed here as dashed black lines) which mark the boundary of the 95% confidence bands of the normal distribution and a red line which is a cubic polynomial fitted to the data points. Depending on the shape of this red line different assertions as to the fit or misfit of the model can be made (Stasinopoulos et al., 2017, p. 428). An ideally fitting model would display a horizontal red line. The Y -coordinates of each point indicate the deviation from the expected values. The values on the X -axis (labeled “Unit normal quantile”) are the number of standard deviations from the mean of the standard normal distribution. If a model is well-defined, we expect its residuals to be normally distributed. The data points should be centered around the horizontal line at $Y = 0$ and 95% of the residuals should be located within the confidence bands.

An inspection of the worm plot shown in Figure 3.5 shows a clear misfit of the weighted linear regression model in the tails of the distribution. The residuals in the more extreme quantiles of the distribution (anywhere below -1.9 and above approximately 1.8 standard deviations from the mean) almost entirely fall outside of the 95% confidence bands indicated by the grey area. The resulting S-shape of the worm plot indicates leptokurtosis, which means that the tails of the distribution of residuals are too heavy. The weighted linear regression model is therefore too light in the tails. Additionally, one may note that there were 2 data points (observations 156 and 2912) that displayed a deviation of 1.3 and 1.95 at approximately 3.3 and 3.6 standard deviations from the mean, respectively, that were cut off from the chart in order to make it more readable. These children have a stunting z-score of 3.67 and 3.95 respectively, which means that not only are these children not affected by stunting in any way, they are also much taller than almost all of the other kids and can therefore be considered statistical outliers.

Figure 3.6: Bucket plot of the residuals of the weighted linear regression model WLR. We can see a clear indication of excess kurtosis in the residuals, emphasizing the misfit of the WLR.

In addition to the worm plot in Figure 3.5 the bucket plot shown in Figure 3.6 clearly shows an excess kurtosis in the residuals of the weighted linear regression model. Bucket plots will be explained in more detail in Section 4.3.1 of this thesis; for now, it suffices to note that all red points (which signify the residuals of the weighted linear regression model) lie outside of the light-grey area in the middle, clearly indicating a model misfit. In sum we can conclude that the weighted linear regression model is unfit to adequately explain the variation of the z-scores of children which are more heavily affected by stunting (exhibiting z-scores of -2 and lower).

3.4.3 Presence of Heteroscedasticity in the Residuals

A closer inspection of the residuals from the weighted linear regression model shows that there is heteroscedasticity present in some of the covariates. Figure 3.7 shows a scatterplot of the residuals of the weighted linear regression model versus the mother’s age in years.

Figure 3.7: Scatter plot of the residuals of the weighted linear regression model vs. mother's age. The residuals appear to be distributed around the blue trend line in a lens-like shape, indicating some presence of heteroscedasticity.

The lens-like distribution of the residuals around the blue trend line seems to indicate some presence of heteroscedasticity. We can see an increase in the variance of the residuals from the around 20 to 30 years and an subsequent decrease in the variance around 38 years of age. This could be due to a smaller sample size around the ages of 20 years and below, as well as 44 years and above. In order to examine this observation, a Breusch-Pagan test (Breusch and Pagan, 1979) was conducted for the V012 regressor which yielded a p-value of 0.066. The Breusch-Pagan test therefore fails to reject the null hypothesis (no presence of heteroscedasticity) at a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$, but does so at a level of $\alpha = 0.1$.

In order to check whether the residuals of any other regressors exhibit heteroscedasticity, further Breusch-Pagan tests were conducted. The results are displayed in Table 3.3.

Regressor	LM	df	p-value
age_months	9.3365	1	0.002246
B0	1.2604	1	0.2616
B4	2.4071	1	0.1208
BORD	14.563	3	0.002231
c_anem	6.1526	1	0.01312
child_deaths	8.3434	1	0.003871
HV009	7.9776	1	0.004736
HV014	7.2967	1	0.006908
m_anem	1.1633	1	0.2808
M14	0.99466	1	0.3186
(M14) ²	0.94783	1	0.3303
V012	3.3767	1	0.06612
V102	3.9941	1	0.04566
V133	2.9035	1	0.08839
V190	5.897	4	0.207
Overall model	46.395	20	0.0007112

Table 3.3: Results of the Breusch-Pagan tests conducted on the regressors of the weighted linear regression model WLR, as well as the overall model itself. LM is the value of the test statistic, df is the degrees of freedom. The residuals of 7 out of 15 regressors of the weighted linear regression model are heteroscedastic at a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ (highlighted in yellow).

The residuals of 7 out of 15 regressors, as well as the overall model itself (including all regressors), exhibit signs of heteroscedasticity. The weighted linear regression model WLR in its current form violates the MLR.5 assumption and is therefore unfit to describe the dataset at hand. Any inference made via this model is therefore invalid.

3.4.4 Conclusion

The results from this analysis clearly show the limitations and misfit of a standard linear regression model. This indicates the need for a more complex class of regression models that allow us to explicitly model the tails of a distribution: in this case the socio-economic, nutritional and environmental determinants that cause Rwandan children to become heavily stunted. The Generalized Additive Model for Location, Scale and Shape (GAMLSS), which is introduced in the following chapter, offers a feasible solution to this issue. In addition the GAMLSS is able to explicitly model heteroscedasticity which, as seen in Section 3.4.3, is present in the data and violates the MLR.5 assumption of the standard linear regression model.

4 Generalized Additive Models for Location, Scale and Shape — GAMLSS

4.1 Methodology

The Generalized Additive Models for Location, Scale and Shape (GAMLSS) were introduced by Rigby and Stasinopoulos (2005) and are a class of semi-parametric distributional regression models. They extend the framework of Generalized Additive Models introduced by Hastie and Tibshirani (1990) in multiple ways, specifically in that they relax the assumption that the response variable needs to follow a distribution from the exponential family. In the GAMLSS framework, a response variable can take follow any parametric distribution, be it continuous or discrete. Most characteristically, GAMLSS allow for an explicit modelling of not only the mean, but also additional parameters of a distribution (such as the variance, skewness and kurtosis) via separate regression formulas. This makes it possible to tackle a much broader range of problems, such as heteroscedasticity in the residuals of the response variables, modeling skewed, platy- or leptokurtic data or inflation and dispersion issues in discrete response variables (Stasinopoulos et al., 2024, p. xiii).

4.1.1 Definition

Let \mathbf{Y} be a vector of independent response variable observations and $\mathcal{D}(\mu, \sigma, \nu, \tau)$ be a distribution with parameters μ (location), σ (standard deviation), ν (skewness) and τ (kurtosis).

$$\mathbf{Y} \stackrel{ind}{\sim} \mathcal{D}(\mu_i, \sigma_i, \nu_i, \tau_i) \quad \text{for } i = 1, \dots, n \quad (4.1)$$

Further, let $g_k(\cdot)$, $k = 1, 2, 3, 4$ be known monotonous link functions that connect all observations $y_i \in \mathbf{Y}$ to a set of regressors in an additive way. Equation (4.2) then defines the GAMLSS as

$$\begin{aligned}
 g_1(\mu) &= \eta_1 = \mathbf{X}_1\boldsymbol{\beta}_1 + \sum_{j=1}^{J_1} \mathbf{Z}_{1j}\boldsymbol{\gamma}_{1j}, \\
 g_2(\sigma) &= \eta_2 = \mathbf{X}_2\boldsymbol{\beta}_2 + \sum_{j=1}^{J_2} \mathbf{Z}_{2j}\boldsymbol{\gamma}_{2j}, \\
 g_3(\nu) &= \eta_3 = \mathbf{X}_3\boldsymbol{\beta}_3 + \sum_{j=1}^{J_3} \mathbf{Z}_{3j}\boldsymbol{\gamma}_{3j}, \\
 g_4(\tau) &= \eta_4 = \mathbf{X}_4\boldsymbol{\beta}_4 + \sum_{j=1}^{J_4} \mathbf{Z}_{4j}\boldsymbol{\gamma}_{4j},
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.2}$$

where \mathbf{X}_k are the fixed effects design matrices of the k -th parameter, \mathbf{Z}_{kj} are the random effects design matrices of the k -th parameter, J_k are the number of random effects per parameter and $\boldsymbol{\beta}_k$ and $\boldsymbol{\gamma}_{kj}$ are coefficient vectors of the fixed and random effects, respectively (Stasinopoulos et al., 2017, p. 24). The η_k are called the *predictors* of the k -th parameter. If there are no random effects, Equation (4.2) simplifies to

$$\begin{aligned}
 g_1(\mu) &= \eta_1 = \mathbf{X}_1\boldsymbol{\beta}_1, \\
 g_2(\sigma) &= \eta_2 = \mathbf{X}_2\boldsymbol{\beta}_2, \\
 g_3(\nu) &= \eta_3 = \mathbf{X}_3\boldsymbol{\beta}_3, \\
 g_4(\tau) &= \eta_4 = \mathbf{X}_4\boldsymbol{\beta}_4.
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.3}$$

The model defined in Equation (4.2) is also referred to as the *random effects GAMLSS*, while the model described in Equation (4.3) is also called the *parametric GAMLSS* (Stasinopoulos et al., 2017, p. 61).

In the parametric GAMLSS model, fitting of the parameters of Equation (4.3) is achieved via maximum likelihood estimation. The likelihood function L is defined as

$$L(\mu, \sigma, \nu, \tau) = \prod_{i=1}^n f(y_i | \mu_i, \sigma_i, \nu_i, \tau_i), \tag{4.4}$$

and the log likelihood function ℓ as

$$\ell = \sum_{i=1}^n \log f(y_i | \mu_i, \sigma_i, \nu_i, \tau_i). \quad (4.5)$$

The fitting of the parameters of the random effects GAMLSS model outlined in Equation (4.2) is achieved via a maximum penalized likelihood estimation. The penalty is quadratic in nature and is defined as $\gamma^\top \mathbf{G}(\lambda)\gamma$, where λ is a vector or scalar of hyperparameters that adjust the amount of smoothing needed to achieve a fit (Stasinopoulos et al., 2017, p. 60) and \mathbf{G} is a known matrix $\mathbf{D}_k^\top \mathbf{D}_k$, where \mathbf{D}_k is a difference matrix of size $(p - k) \times p$ dependent on the order k (Stasinopoulos et al., 2017, p. 268). p is the number of columns in the design matrix \mathbf{X}_k , i.e. the number of regressors in the parameter k (Stasinopoulos et al., 2017, p. xx).

The penalized likelihood function ℓ_p for the random effects GAMLSS model in Equation (4.2) is defined as

$$\ell_p = \ell - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^4 \sum_{j=1}^{J_k} \gamma_{kj}^\top \mathbf{G}_{kj}(\lambda_{kj}) \gamma_{kj}, \quad (4.6)$$

(Stasinopoulos et al., 2017, p. 61) where ℓ is the log likelihood as defined in Equation (4.5). The maximization of the penalized log likelihood is performed either via the CG algorithm (an extension of the Cole and Green (1992) algorithm) or the RS algorithm, an extended version of the algorithm introduced by Rigby and Stasinopoulos (1996a) and Rigby and Stasinopoulos (1996b).

4.1.2 The Generalized Akaike Information Criterion

The Generalized Akaike Information Criterion (GAIC) is a variation of the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) introduced by Akaike (1974). The GAIC penalizes additional parameters with κ and is defined as

$$\text{GAIC}(\kappa) = -2\hat{\ell} + (\kappa \cdot \text{df}), \quad (4.7)$$

where $\hat{\ell}$ is the estimated log likelihood and df is the degrees of freedom (Stasinopoulos et al., 2017, p. 13). The GAIC is a widely used measure to compare two or more models with one another. The model with the lower GAIC value is considered the “better” one. With a value of $\kappa = 2$ Equation (4.7) represents the AIC, when $\kappa = \log(n)$ it represents the Bayesian Information Criterion BIC (Schwarz, 1978).

When $\kappa = 3.84$ the model complexity is penalized by the critical value of a χ_1^2 distribution with 1 degree of freedom at a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$.

4.2 Distribution Selection

On the one hand, the intricacy of the GAMLSS approach allows for a better representation of the complex nature of reality. On the other hand, it leads to a number of challenges that have to be overcome when creating a distributional regression model. The most important choice is that of the underlying distribution the data at hand originates from. As described in Section 2.2, the target variable of our regression model is the stunting z-score. The stunting z-score in the extracted data ranges between -5.93 and 3.95 . Additionally, as seen in Figure 3.2, the z-scores are approximately normally distributed. We therefore need to make a choice from the set of continuous distributions defined on $\mathbb{R} = (-\infty, \infty)$. The `gamlss` package in R contains a large number of such distributions to choose from (Rigby et al., 2019, p. 61). Rigby and Stasinopoulos (2018) suggest starting with a simple model and building up the complexity until the residuals of the GAMLSS model are approximately normally distributed (Rigby et al., 2019, p. 69). This means that distributions with a lower number of parameters would be fitted first and, if the residuals are not approximately normally distributed, more complex models are needed. The model selection process described in this section is guided by the “Recipe for Model Selection” described in Stasinopoulos et al. (2024, pp. 97–98).

A sensible “standard distribution” to start from is the normal distribution, as it has only 2 parameters (μ for location and σ for scale) and is defined on the real line of numbers. A preliminary GAMLSS model based on the normal distribution was fitted to the extracted data via the `gamlss()` command in R. The `chooseDist()` command was run on this preliminary model in order to determine the fit of all other possible parametric distributions defined on the real line of numbers. All possible regressors (as per Section 3.2.3) were allowed to be included in any of the parameters (μ for location, σ for variance/standard deviation, ν for skewness and τ for kurtosis). The `chooseDist()` command yields a list of all applicable distributions¹ along with their GAIC values (with penalty $k = 2$ for AIC, $k = 3.84$ for χ_1^2 and $k = \log(n) = 8.13$ for BIC). The RS-algorithm was chosen and the limit of iterations set to 500. 3 of the 27 distributions (namely EGB2, JSU and JSUo) did not converge after the limit of 500 iterations of the RS-algorithm, so the `gamlss()`

¹The names of the distributions were abbreviated according to the R output of the `chooseDist()` function; see Table A.1 in the Appendix for clarification.

command for these distributions was run again with a higher limit. While the EGB2 model converged after 1039 and the JSUo model after 5294 iterations, the JSU model did not yield a satisfactory result, its global deviance jumping heavily between iterations, never converging towards a final value. The ultimate GAIC values of this model could therefore not be determined beyond doubt; it will thus not be examined any further. The results from the `chooseDist()` function are shown in Table 4.1.

A preliminary model selection was conducted based on these results. The models based on the normal distribution (abbreviated as NO), as well as the JSUo and EGB2 models were chosen for further examination.

Distribution	GAIC values		
	$k = 2$	$k = 3.84$	$k = 8.13$
JSUo	10153.8	10289.96	10607.42
EGB2	10156.46	10292.62	10610.08
ST5	10176.27	10312.43	10629.89
TF2	10213.42	10314.62	10550.57
SST	10215.41	10351.57	10669.03
SN1	10234.81	10336.01	10571.96
SEP2	10246.98	10383.14	10700.6
ST2	10251.25	10387.41	10704.87
SEP1	10252.65	10388.81	10706.27
GT	10265.61	10401.77	10719.23
TF	10267.24	10368.44	10604.39
ST4	10270.83	10406.99	10724.45
PE2	10273.14	10374.34	10610.29
PE	10274.29	10375.49	10611.44
ST3	10276.56	10412.72	10730.18
SEP4	10277.19	10413.35	10730.81
SEP3	10277.22	10413.38	10730.84
SN2	10278.18	10379.38	10615.33
NO	10280.7	10346.94	10501.38
SHASH	10280.78	10416.94	10734.4
SHASHo2	10281.9	10418.06	10735.52
LO	10282.01	10348.25	10502.69
SHASHo	10282.13	10418.29	10735.75
NET	10456.7	10522.94	10677.38

RG	10837.85	10904.09	11058.53
GU	11013.05	11079.29	11233.73
JSU	– Not established beyond doubt –		

Table 4.1: Results from the `chooseDist()` function. The corresponding GAIC values of all distributions show that the models based on the JSUo and the EGB2 distributions have the lowest GAIC values, whereas the NO model based on the normal distribution has the lowest BIC value (all highlighted in yellow). The GAIC values of the JSU distribution could not be established due to non-convergence.

The JSUo model is a distributional regression model based on the 4 parameter Johnson’s S_u distribution presented by Johnson (1949). This distribution is a transformation of the normal distribution with the probability density function

$$f(y|\mu, \sigma, \nu, \tau) = \frac{\tau}{\sigma(z^2 + 1)^{\frac{1}{2}} \sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{2}r^2\right], \quad (4.8)$$

where $z = \frac{(y-\mu)}{\sigma}$ and $r = \nu + \tau \sinh^{-1}(z)$ (see Rigby et al., 2019, pp. 389–390).

The full JSUo model is defined as:

$$\text{HW70} \sim \text{JSUo}(\mu, \sigma, \nu, \tau)$$

$$\mu = \eta_\mu = \mathbf{X}_1 \boldsymbol{\beta}_\mu,$$

$$\log(\sigma) = \eta_\sigma = \mathbf{X}_2 \boldsymbol{\beta}_\sigma,$$

$$\nu = \eta_\nu = \mathbf{X}_3 \boldsymbol{\beta}_\nu,$$

$$\log(\tau) = \eta_\tau = \mathbf{X}_4 \boldsymbol{\beta}_\tau,$$

where $\mathbf{X}_k, k = 1, 2, 3, 4$ are the design matrices containing the individual data of all observations in regards to all included regressors. The $\beta_p, p = \mu, \sigma, \nu, \tau$ are vectors of the coefficients (see Equation (4.2)).

The EGB2 model is based on the 4 parameter Exponential Generalized Beta Type 2 distribution first introduced by McDonald and Xu (1995, p. 141). The probability density function is defined as

$$f(y|\mu, \sigma, \nu, \tau) = e^{\nu z} \left[|\sigma| B(\nu, \tau) (1 + e^z)^{\nu+\tau} \right]^{-1}, \quad (4.9)$$

where $z = \frac{(y-\mu)}{\sigma}$ and B is the beta function (see Rigby et al., 2019, pp. 385–386).

The full EGB2 model is defined as:

$$\text{HW70} \sim \text{EGB2}(\mu, \sigma, \nu, \tau)$$

$$\mu = \eta_\mu = \mathbf{X}_1\boldsymbol{\beta}_\mu,$$

$$\log(\sigma) = \eta_\sigma = \mathbf{X}_2\boldsymbol{\beta}_\sigma,$$

$$\log(\nu) = \eta_\nu = \mathbf{X}_3\boldsymbol{\beta}_\nu,$$

$$\log(\tau) = \eta_\tau = \mathbf{X}_4\boldsymbol{\beta}_\tau.$$

Both density functions are similar in shape to a normal distribution, however they allow for an explicit modelling of the skewness and kurtosis via the ν and τ parameters, respectively. Figures A.4 and A.5 in the Appendix show the resulting change in shape when varying the ν and τ parameters. Figures 4.1, 4.2 and 4.3 show worm plots of the residuals of the NO, JSUo and EGB2 models.

The worm plot shown in Figure 4.1 indicates strong leptokurtosis in the NO model, which means that the tails of the distribution of residuals are too heavy. The fitted NO model therefore assigns too little weight to the tails of its distribution. This is to be expected, as the normal distribution per definition does not allow for an explicit modelling of the upper- and lowermost quantiles. While most of the data points lie within the 95% confidence band, the model does not yield satisfactory results with regards to the children who are most severely affected by stunting. Again, observations 156 and 2912 lie far outside of the confidence band and were cut off to make the plot easier to interpret. While this model will most likely be outperformed by both the EGB2 and JSUo models which both allow for the skewness and kurtosis to be modeled via the ν and τ parameters, it will be kept as a reference model in order to compare it to the other 2 candidate models. An additional variable selection for this model will be conducted in Section 4.3.

Figure 4.1: Worm plot of the residuals of the preliminary NO model. While most residuals lay within the 95% confidence band, we can see a strong S-shape indicating strong leptokurtosis, meaning that the tails of the distribution of residuals of residuals are too heavy. Children with more extreme z-scores are therefore inadequately captured by this model.

A similar picture is displayed in Figure 4.2. While the worm plot of the residuals of the JSUo model indicates a slightly better fit in the lowermost quantiles of the distribution (the datapoints all lie within the 95% confidence band), the uppermost quantiles of the distribution are inadequately modelled. Again we can see strong evidence of leptokurtosis, which might however be fixed with a variable selection as will be conducted in Section 4.3.

Figure 4.2: Worm plot of the residuals of the preliminary JSUo model. While this model captures the children with z-scores in the lower extreme quantiles, the z-scores of children with higher than usual z-scores are not adequately captured in this model. Additionally, a strong S-shape of the residuals is present, again indicating strong leptokurtosis.

Finally, the best fit seems to be achieved via the EGB2 model. The worm plot in Figure 4.3 displays mild leptokurtosis in the model, but almost all data points are captured within the 95% confidence band. Still, a variable selection will be conducted in the next section in order to further improve the fit and derive a final model to be interpreted.

Figure 4.3: Worm plot of the residuals of the preliminary EGB2 model. This model appears to adequately capture almost all observations, but still exhibits a slight S-shape indicating a light leptokurtosis.

4.3 Covariate Selection

Stasinopoulos et al. (2024, pp. 95–96) note that there are several different strategies that can be chosen in order to select a set of covariates to be included in the formulas of the regression parameters. The authors recommend a step-wise approach (mixed forward and backward selection) which is what will be used in this section. A “hierarchy” between the parameters is to be followed: they recommend to start with the location parameter, followed by the scale and (if applicable) the skewness and kurtosis parameters in this order. This is to avoid overfitting a model, as large residuals due to an improperly fitted parameter (e.g. wrongly fitted location) may lead to an overcompensation through another parameter (e.g. the scale).

The step-wise variable selection works as follows:

- Forward selection of the location (μ) parameter, iteratively checking the GAIC values with penalty $k = 2$ and in each iteration including the regressor that leads to the highest decrease in the GAIC value compared to the current model.

This is repeated until no further decrease in the GAIC value is achieved or all possible regressors have been added to the model

- Forward selection of the scale (σ) parameter in the same way
- Forward selection of the skewness parameter (ν)
- Forward selection of the kurtosis parameter (τ)
- Backward selection of the skewness parameter: the regressors of the skewness parameter are eliminated one by one, thereby checking whether eliminating parameter j leads to a decrease in the GAIC value
- Backward selection of the scale parameter in the same way
- Backward selection of the location parameter

The result of this procedure is a model that best describes the data at hand with a minimum number of regressors influencing each parameter. This step-wise variable selection procedure was run for all 3 candidate models, yielding the `NO_3step`, `JSUo_7step` and `EGB2_7step` models. The resulting worm plots of the residuals are shown in Figures 4.4a, 4.5a and 4.5b.

4.3.1 Asserting Model Kurtosis and Skewness via the Bucket Plot

A number of bucket plots, a graphical tool introduced by De Bastiani et al. (2022), were created for the 3 candidate models to assess each model's fit in terms of the skewness and kurtosis. The tails of the distribution are of special interest here as these contain the children most severely affected by stunting (exhibiting a z -score of -3 and lower) and should therefore be explicitly modeled. Bucket plots are very useful in determining whether the skewness and kurtosis of a distribution are appropriately modeled, which means that the residuals of a fitted distribution are normally distributed. Specifically, the normalized quantile residuals (Dunn and Smyth, 1996) are examined, as these will always follow a standard normal distribution if the underlying regression model is correctly specified, regardless of distribution chosen (Stasinopoulos et al., 2017, pp. 418–419, 422).

The normalized quantile residuals are defined as

$$\hat{r}_i = \Phi^{-1}(\hat{u}_i), \quad (4.10)$$

where $\Phi^{-1}(\cdot)$ is the inverse cumulative distribution function of the standard normal distribution and $\hat{u}_i = F(y_i; \hat{\mu}_i, \hat{\sigma}_i, \hat{\nu}_i, \hat{\tau}_i)$ for observations $i = 1, \dots, n$ is the fitted cumulative distribution function of the GAMLSS model.

Bucket plots consist of a black bucket-shaped area that indicates the possible excess skewness and kurtosis, an oval light-grey region in the middle of the bucket which is a 95% confidence area of the Jarque-Bera test (Jarque and Bera, 1980), which checks whether the residuals are normally distributed, and a sample of 99 randomly picked data points whose excess skewness and kurtosis determines their position in the bucket. If the residuals are normally distributed, we expect approximately 95% of these points to lie within the light-grey area: there should be approximately zero excess skewness and kurtosis. If this is not the case, the model needs to be adjusted: points to the left or right of this area indicate a misfit in the skewness and points above or below the area indicate a misfit in the kurtosis of the fitted distribution.

4.3.2 Diagnostic Plots of the NO_3step Model

Figure 4.4: (a) Worm plot of the residuals of the final NO_3step model. The resulting variable selection produced almost no change in the tails of the distribution. The model is still heavily leptokurtic, which makes sense as the normal distribution does not allow for an explicit modelling of the tails of the distribution. (b) Bucket plot of the Residuals of the final NO_3step model. Almost all of the randomly sampled residuals lie outside of the light-grey confidence area to the top right. This indicates an excess kurtosis and a positive skewness in the residuals.

Figure 4.4a shows almost no change in the residuals of the `NO` model after conducting the 3-step variable selection. The model is still heavily leptokurtic, which means that the residuals in the tails are still too high. This is to be expected, as the normal distribution does not allow for an explicit modelling of the tails of the distribution. The bucket plot shown in Figure 4.4b confirms this observation: almost all of the randomly sampled residuals lie outside to the top right of the 95% confidence area. This indicates that the `NO_3step` model assigns too little weight to the tails of its distribution. In addition to the excess kurtosis a slight positive skewness in the residuals can be observed, indicating that some adjustments in the skewness parameter need to be conducted.

4.3.3 Resulting JSUo and EGB2 Models from the 7-Step Variable Selection Procedure

At first glance, running the 7-step variable selection procedure outlined in Section 4.3 yields reasonably well-fitting models with low AIC values — 10128.16 for the `EGB2_7step` model and 10141.37 for the `JSUo_7step` model (the `NO_3step` model in contrast has an AIC value of 10260.98). Especially the `EGB2_7step` model shows a reduced leptokurtosis and almost all residuals are located within the 95% confidence band (see Figure 4.5a). The `JSUo` model in contrast shows signs of stronger leptokurtosis, as can be seen from the S shape of the red line in Figure 4.5b. Many of the residuals of the uppermost quantiles lie outside of the 95% confidence interval, so the `JSUo` model, as yielded by the 7-step variable selection procedure, fails to adequately explain the measures of children who have higher than usual z-scores (above 2 standard deviations from the reference mean).

Despite the apparent sound model quality (especially that of the `EGB2_7step` model) generating a `summary()` of the `EGB2_7step` and `JSUo_7step` models showed that the results of both of these models contradict the findings of prior research (see Section 3.1 of this thesis). A comparison of both `summary()` outputs is listed in Table 4.2. Most apparent is the supposed positive influence on the mean z-score of children who were born as twins. According to the `JSUo_7step` model this on average increases the individual z-score by 2.518 units, although the regressor is not statistically significant at the $\alpha = 0.05$ level. A regressor that does appear to be statistically significant is the binary variable `child_deaths` which is set to 1 if a mother has lost any children prior to the survey. According to the `JSUo_7step` model, the loss of 1 or more children *positively* affects the z-scores of the remaining siblings by a value of 1.935. Keeping in mind that stunting is defined as a child having a height-for-age z-score of -2 and lower, this result of the model seems highly

implausible. The number of siblings aged 5 and under is also supposedly a positive factor contributing to the child's z-score by a value of 0.591 per additional child. In light of resource scarcity, especially among the poorest of families, this result seems highly dubious. One may also note the intercept of the μ parameter which is set to a value of -8.606 (!): according to the `JSUo_7step` model, a child from a medium wealth family, whose mother did not receive any education, is not part of a twin birth, etc. (all individual characteristics set to the baseline values and, for demonstration purposes, ignoring the mother's age) would have an extremely low mean z-score of -8.606 . The lowest z-score in the extracted data is reported to be -5.93 , which, given the definition of the z-score, appears almost impossible. Children affected this heavily by undernutrition would most likely have died before setting this somber record. The coefficients of the covariates of the σ , ν and τ parameters also appear implausible. According to the `JSUo_7step` model, growing up in an urban region of Rwanda massively affects the variance of z-scores by a factor of 1.222. This means that the z-scores of children who share the same characteristics but live in rural compared to urban areas of the country may vary by as much as 1.222 units from the mean. Moreover, according to the coefficient of the household region regressor in the τ parameter, growing up in an urban region increases the risk of both extreme malnutrition and above-average growth. Needless to say, the `JSUo_7step` model in its current form needs to be adjusted to better reflect real-world conditions.

The `EGB2_7step` model shows results that seem more promising, yet still far removed from any prior research findings. While the `EGB2_7step` model predicts higher z-scores with increasing household wealth (just like the `JSUo_7step` model), it paints a contradictory picture in regards to the prior loss of children. The `EGB2` model predicts lower z-scores if a mother has lost 1 or more children, but rising z-scores for any additional living sibling aged 5 or under. The household region plays almost no role in the child's z-score, neither in terms of coefficient or p-value, neither in the μ nor in the σ parameter. The `EGB2_7step` model also assigns completely different covariates to the τ parameter compared to the `JSUo_7step` model, attributing the change in the most extreme quantiles of the distribution to anemia in children, a low birth index and the number of siblings aged 5 and under, instead of the household region or the death of any siblings like the `JSUo_7step` model predicts.

In addition, the 7-step variable selection procedure eliminated core variables of interest from both the `JSUo` and the `EGB2_7step` model which were shown to have a significant impact on the stunting z-scores of children in other countries. The maternal anemia category (either anemic or not) is not included in any of the 2 models and the `EGB2_7step` model does not differentiate whether there are any

effects on the mean z-score with respect to the gender, the size of the family or whether the child is anemic.

Figure 4.5: (a) Worm Plot of the Residuals of the EGB2_7step model after running the 7-step variable selection. (b) Worm Plot of the Residuals of the JSUo_7step model after running the 7-step variable selection.

Figure 4.6: Bucket plot of the residuals of the `JSUo_7step` and `EGB2_7step` models (abbreviated as *JSUo* and *EGB2* for better readability) after running the 7-step variable selection. While the `EGB2_7step` model shows almost no skewness in the residuals, both the `JSUo_7step` and the `EGB2_7step` models suffer from leptokurtosis, which is a bit more prominent in the `JSUo_7step` model.

Additional information can be gathered from the bucket plot shown in Figure 4.6. The `EGB2_7step` model displays almost no skewness in the residuals, though the residuals are quite spread out, half of them residing within the 95% confidence area, half of them outside of it. Some excess kurtosis in the residuals can be noted, which means that the observations of children with more extreme z-scores are not properly accounted for (too little weight is attributed to these observations in the `EGB2_7step` model, leading to leptokurtosis in the residuals). Much less well-fitting is the `JSUo_7step` model, which displays both an excess kurtosis as well as a high positive skewness in the residuals. Just like in the `EGB2_7step` model, more extreme observations of z-scores are improperly accounted for and the positive skewness of the residuals indicates a misspecification of the ν parameter of the model.

Due to the obvious misfit of both models, a manual review of the parameter specifications of both models will be conducted in the next section in order to construct 2 candidate models that more accurately reflect the real-world conditions.

JSUo_7step Model				EGB2_7step Model			
Mu parameters	Category	Estimate	p-value	Mu parameters	Category	Estimate	p-value
(Intercept)		-8.606	< 0.0001	(Intercept)		-4.722	< 0.0001
Household wealth quintile <i>(compared to "Middle")</i>	Poorest	-0.326	< 0.0001	Household wealth quintile <i>(compared to "Middle")</i>	Poorest	-0.322	< 0.0001
	Poor	-0.211	0.0001		Poor	-0.219	< 0.0001
	Richer	0.087	0.1252		Richer	0.086	0.1240
	Richest	0.573	< 0.0001		Richest	0.564	< 0.0001
Maternal education		0.030	< 0.0001	Maternal education (years)		0.028	< 0.0001
Prenatal visits squared		0.016	< 0.0001	Prenatal visits squared		0.011	< 0.0001
Twin birth	Yes	2.518	0.0805				
No. of household members		0.140	0.1669				
Mother had children die	Yes	1.935	0.0340	Mother had children die	Yes	-0.127	0.0366
Household region	Urban	0.197	0.0019	Household region	Urban	0.090	0.1055
Child's age (months)		0.138	< 0.0001	Child's age (months)		0.043	< 0.0001
Mother's age (years)		0.072	0.0126	Mother's age (years)		0.024	0.0042
Child is anemic	Yes	-0.100	0.0812				
No. of siblings 5 and under		0.591	0.0270	No. of siblings 5 and under		0.250	0.0088
Sigma parameters	Category	Estimate	p-value	Sigma parameters	Category	Estimate	p-value
(Intercept)		1.971	< 0.0001	(Intercept)		0.786	< 0.0001
Birth order <i>(Index 1 = no influence)</i>	2 or 3	0.041	0.0230	Birth order <i>(Index 1 = no influence)</i>	2 or 3	-0.003	0.9344
	4 or 5	0.071	0.0050		4 or 5	0.060	0.2039
	6+	0.093	0.0034		6+	0.136	0.0152
Child's age (months)		-0.006	< 0.0001	Child's age (months)		-0.022	< 0.0001
No. of siblings 5 and under		0.017	0.1196	No. of siblings 5 and under		0.115	< 0.0001
Child is anemic	Yes	0.049	0.0084	Child is anemic	Yes	0.130	0.0009
Household region	Urban	1.222	0.0338	Household region	Urban	0.056	0.0741
Mother had children die		0.610	0.0059	Mother had children die		0.069	0.0679
Nu parameters	Category	Estimate	p-value	Nu parameters	Category	Estimate	p-value
(Intercept)		-6.883	< 0.0001	(Intercept)		3.408	< 0.0001
Child's age (months)		0.151	< 0.0001	Child's age (months)		-0.050	< 0.0001
No. of household members		0.146	0.1438				
Gender of child	Male	0.211	< 0.0001	Gender of child	Male	-0.145	< 0.0001
Mother's age (years)		0.065	0.0229	Mother's age (years)		-0.009	0.0789
No. of siblings 5 and under		0.639	0.0143				
Mother had children die	Yes	1.817	0.0285				
Twin birth	Yes	2.825	0.0303				
Tau parameters	Category	Estimate	p-value	Tau parameters	Category	Estimate	p-value
(Intercept)		1.913	< 0.0001	(Intercept)		1.685	< 0.0001
Household region	Urban	1.133	0.0455	Child's age (months)		-0.024	0.000258
Mother had children die	Yes	0.517	0.0094	No. of siblings 5 and under		0.231	< 0.0001
Prenatal visits		-0.027	0.0196	Child is anemic	Yes	0.142	0.000584
Prenatal visits squared		0.004	0.1502	Twin birth	Yes	0.277	< 0.0001
Mother's age (years)		0.002	0.1857	Birth order	2 or 3	0.020	0.66543
				<i>(Index 1 = no influence)</i>	4 or 5	0.107	0.068807
					6+	0.173	0.014126

Table 4.2: Summary of the JSUo_7step and EGB2_7step models after 7-step variable selection procedure. Many of the coefficients of the regressors disagree with prior research findings. A large number of variables of core interest, such as the child's gender, the effect of the birth order on the mean z-scores or the maternal anemia values, were eliminated. A manual adjustment of the parameters will have to be conducted.

4.3.4 Adjustments to the JSUo_7step and EGB2_7step Models

The results from Section 4.3.3 suggest that amendments to the variable selection have to be conducted. This is because the parameters within GAMLSS models are

often interdependent (Stasinopoulos et al., 2024, p. 107): a change in one parameter (for example the skewness parameter ν) might significantly affect another parameter (for example the location parameter μ). Even though the residuals appear to be (mostly) normally distributed (especially with regards to the EGB2_7step model), the resulting coefficients indicate highly unlikely relationships. And despite the addition of regressors to the ν parameter significantly decreasing the AIC values of both models during the 7-step variable selection procedure, it is possible that the interplay of variables between the individual parameters leads to numerical instability, causing the underlying max-likelihood algorithm to converge towards local minima. Harrell (2015, pp. 67–68) notably criticizes the step-wise inclusion and elimination of covariates in regression models, stating that this method leads to a bias in the standard errors and confidence intervals, causing misleadingly low p-values, deceptively high coefficients of included regressors and does not take collinearity between regressors into account (which, as it may be added here, appears to be an issue with the GAMLSS based models of this thesis).

It was therefore decided to revert the 7-step procedure back to the results of step 2 (having added covariates to the μ and σ parameters of the models) and leaving the skewness parameter ν at the intercept instead of proceeding with the AIC-based inclusion of regressors in step 3. A manual addition of variables to the kurtosis parameter τ was conducted, as well as adding any covariate outlined in Section 3.2.3 to the μ parameter which yielded the revised JSUo_rev and EGB2_rev models:

JSUo_rev:

$$\text{HW70}_i \sim \text{JSUo}(\mu_i, \sigma_i, \nu_i, \tau_i)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_i = \eta_{\mu,i} = & \beta_{\mu,0} + \beta_{\mu,1}\text{V190}_i + \beta_{\mu,2}\text{V133}_i + \beta_{\mu,3}\text{M14_sq}_i + \beta_{\mu,4}\text{B4}_i + \beta_{\mu,5}\text{B0}_i \\ & + \beta_{\mu,6}\text{HV009}_i + \beta_{\mu,7}\text{child_deaths}_i + \beta_{\mu,8}\text{V102}_i \\ & + \beta_{\mu,9}\text{age_months}_i + \beta_{\mu,10}\text{V012}_i + \beta_{\mu,11}\text{c_anem}_i \\ & + \beta_{\mu,12}\text{m_anem}_i + \beta_{\mu,13}\text{BORD}_i + \beta_{\mu,14}\text{HV014}_i + \beta_{\mu,15}\text{M14}_i, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \log(\sigma_i) = \eta_{\sigma,i} = & \beta_{\sigma,0} + \beta_{\sigma,1}\text{BORD}_i + \beta_{\sigma,2}\text{age_months}_i + \beta_{\sigma,3}\text{HV014}_i + \beta_{\sigma,4}\text{c_anem}_i \\ & + \beta_{\sigma,5}\text{V102}_i + \beta_{\sigma,6}\text{child_deaths}_i, \end{aligned}$$

$$\nu_i = \eta_{\nu,i} = \beta_{\nu,0},$$

$$\log(\tau_i) = \eta_{\tau,i} = \beta_{\tau,0} + \beta_{\tau,1}\text{BORD}_i + \beta_{\tau,2}\text{c_anem}_i,$$

where $i = 1, \dots, n$.

EGB2_rev:

$$HW70_i \sim \text{EGB2}(\mu_i, \sigma_i, \nu_i, \tau_i)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_i = & \eta_{\mu,i} \beta_{\mu,0} + \beta_{\mu,1} \text{V190}_i + \beta_{\mu,2} \text{V133}_i + \beta_{\mu,3} \text{M14_sq}_i + \beta_{\mu,4} \text{B4}_i + \beta_{\mu,5} \text{B0}_i \\ & + \beta_{\mu,6} \text{HV009}_i + \beta_{\mu,7} \text{child_deaths}_i + \beta_{\mu,8} \text{V102}_i \\ & + \beta_{\mu,9} \text{age_months}_i + \beta_{\mu,10} \text{V012}_i + \beta_{\mu,11} \text{c_anem}_i \\ & + \beta_{\mu,12} \text{m_anem}_i + \beta_{\mu,13} \text{BORD}_i + \beta_{\mu,14} \text{HV014}_i + \beta_{\mu,15} \text{M14}_i, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \log(\sigma_i) = \eta_{\sigma,i} = & \beta_{\sigma,0} + \beta_{\sigma,1} \text{BORD}_i + \beta_{\sigma,2} \text{age_months}_i + \beta_{\sigma,3} \text{HV014}_i + \beta_{\sigma,4} \text{c_anem}_i \\ & + \beta_{\sigma,5} \text{V102}_i + \beta_{\sigma,6} \text{child_deaths}_i, \end{aligned}$$

$$\log(\nu_i) = \eta_{\nu,i} = \beta_{\nu,0},$$

$$\log(\tau_i) = \eta_{\tau,i} = \beta_{\tau,0} + \beta_{\tau,1} \text{age_months}_i + \beta_{\tau,2} \text{c_anem}_i + \beta_{\tau,3} \text{B0}_i,$$

where $i = 1, \dots, n$.

It is apparent that, despite being based on different distributions, the selection of parameters for both models is almost identical (merely the τ parameter differs in its selection of covariates). The `EGB2_rev` model (per definition) maps the ν parameter in a logarithmic instead of a linear way to the target variable.

4.4 Final Model Selection and Quantitative Results

As seen in the worm and bucket plots displayed in Figure 4.4 the `NO_3step` model is highly inadequate in modelling the extracted data due to its inherent limitation of being unable to explicitly model skewness and kurtosis. The revised `JSUo_rev` and `EGB2_rev` models, on the other hand, perform much better.

The worm plot shown in Figure 4.7a show that the `JSUo_rev` model adequately represents almost all of the observations with only a single observation (number 2912) lying outside of the 95% confidence band. The red line representing the cubic fit of the residuals is almost perfectly horizontal which means that the kurtosis was adequately accounted for. Almost all residuals are evenly spread around the grey line at a deviation value of 0 which means that the σ parameter is well modeled, too. The bucket plot in Figure 4.7b which compares the `JSUo_rev` model with its former version (the `JSUo_7step` model) yielded by the automatic 7-step variable selection

procedure clearly shows that the revised model is adequate in both the skewness and the kurtosis of the residuals.

The `EGB2_rev` model's worm plot in Figure 4.8a presents similar results. Both the variance (judging by the distribution of the residuals around the 0 deviation-line) and the kurtosis of the underlying data were adequately captured. Observation 2912, which lies outside of the 95% confidence band in the `JSUo_rev` model's worm plot, is now located within the confidence area. Only the μ parameter appears to be a little off, judging by the deviation values of the residuals in the middle of the worm plot (between ± 0.5 standard deviations from the mean). This does not indicate any misspecification of the model, however, as these residuals are still contained within the 95% confidence band. A bucket plot comparing the skewness and the kurtosis of the residuals of the revised `EGB2_rev` and unadjusted `EGB2_7step` models is shown in Figure 4.8b. Both the excess kurtosis and the negative skewness of the residuals of the `EGB2_7step` model are now corrected. The `EGB2_rev` model is therefore correctly specified.

Comparing the output of the `summary()` command applied on both models does show some differences in the coefficients of the different models, though. Table 4.3 in the next section shows a comparison of the results of both models.

Figure 4.7: (a) Worm plot of the final JSUo_rev model after conducting a manual variable selection. (b) Bucket plot of the residuals of the final JSUo_rev model (red) compared to the residuals of the JSUo_7step model yielded from the 7-step variable selection procedure. The positive skewness and excess kurtosis in the residuals have now been resolved.

Figure 4.8: (a) Worm plot of the final EGB2_rev model after conducting a manual variable selection. (b) Bucket plot of the residuals of the final EGB2_rev model (green) compared to the residuals of the EGB2_7step model yielded from the 7-step variable selection procedure (red). The positive skewness and excess kurtosis in the residuals have now been resolved.

4.4.1 Final Results of the Adjusted JSUo and EGB2 Models

JSUo_rev Model				EGB2_rev Model				
Mu parameters	Category	Estimate	p-value	Mu parameters	Category	Estimate	p-value	
(Intercept)		-1.982	< 0.0001	(Intercept)		-2.242	< 0.0001	
Household wealth quintile (compared to "Middle")	Poorest	-0.345	< 0.0001	Household wealth quintile (compared to "Middle")	Poorest	-0.336	< 0.0001	
	Poor	-0.227	< 0.0001		Poor	-0.224	< 0.0001	
	Richer	0.078	0.1706		Richer	0.077	0.1763	
	Richest	0.554	< 0.0001		Richest	0.559	< 0.0001	
Maternal education		0.028	< 0.0001	Maternal education		0.028	< 0.0001	
Prenatal visits squared		0.023	0.0037	Prenatal visits squared		0.023	0.0028	
Gender of child	Male	-0.212	< 0.0001	Gender of child	Male	-0.208	< 0.0001	
Twin birth	Yes	-0.516	< 0.0001	Twin birth	Yes	0.058	0.9012	
No. of household members		-0.011	0.4043	No. of household members		-0.011	0.4163	
Mother had children die	Yes	-0.121	0.0515	Mother had children die	Yes	-0.113	0.0619	
Household region	Urban	0.125	0.0265	Household region	Urban	0.133	0.0159	
Child's age (months)		-0.004	0.0049	Child's age (months)		0.006	0.2256	
Mother's age (years)		0.012	0.0046	Mother's age (years)		0.012	0.0045	
Child is anemic	Yes	-0.11	0.0509	Child is anemic	Yes	0.434	0.3118	
Mother is anemic	Yes	0.015	0.8797	Mother is anemic	Yes	0.004	0.9702	
Birth order (Index 1 = no influence)	2 or 3	-0.031	0.5618	Birth order (Index 1 = no influence)	2 or 3	-0.041	0.4382	
	4 or 5	-0.144	0.0621		4 or 5	-0.145	0.0596	
	6+	-0.228	0.0325		6+	-0.206	0.0495	
No. of siblings 5 and under		-0.073	0.0365	No. of siblings 5 and under		-0.069	0.0476	
No. of prenatal visits		-0.068	0.0704	No. of prenatal visits		-0.07	0.0588	
Sigma parameters	Category	Estimate	p-value	Sigma parameters	Category	Estimate	p-value	
(Intercept)		1.916	0.0028	(Intercept)		-0.0348	0.8250	
Birth order (Index 1 = no influence)	2 or 3	-1.036	0.1134	Birth order (Index 1 = no influence)	2 or 3	-0.0440	0.2000	
	4 or 5	-1.065	0.115		4 or 5	0.0010	0.9809	
	6+	-0.544	0.5064		6+	0.0753	0.1245	
Child's age (months)		-0.002	0.0109	Child's age (months)		0.0001	0.9334	
No. of siblings 5 and under		0.040	0.0347	No. of siblings 5 and under		0.0473	0.0147	
Child is anemic	Yes	0.856	0.2521	Child is anemic	Yes	0.1965	0.0259	
Household region	Urban	0.061	0.0842	Household region	Urban	0.0539	0.1302	
Mother had children die	Yes	0.073	0.0796	Mother had children die	Yes	0.0735	0.0712	
Nu parameters	Category	Estimate	p-value	Nu parameters	Category	Estimate	p-value	
(Intercept)		-0.287	0.0925	(Intercept)		0.963	0.0003	
Tau parameters	Category	Estimate	p-value	Tau parameters	Category	Estimate	p-value	
(Intercept)		1.876	0.0027	(Intercept)		0.518	0.0539	
Birth order (Index 1 = no influence)	2 or 3	-0.937	0.0027	Child's age (months)		0.008	0.0229	
	4 or 5	-0.996	0.1282		Child is anemic	Yes	0.396	0.1649
	6+	-0.595	0.4515		Twin birth	Yes	0.423	0.2030
Child is anemic	Yes	0.747	0.3054					

Table 4.3: Summary of the JSUo_rev and EGB2_rev models after manual variable selection. The models are similar to one another, but they do differ in their choice of covariates included in the τ parameters. Covariates which are statistically significant at a confidence level of $\alpha = 0.05$ are highlighted in yellow.

The 2 revised models are quite similar to one another. Both models indicate a positive relationship between the household wealth and the stunting z-score of the children who live in them. Compared to a household of "middle" wealth, children living in the poorest 20% of households on average have a z-score that is approximately 0.33 units lower. The difference between the "middle" and "richest" households is

even more extreme: growing up in one of the wealthiest households, an average child will have a z-score that is approximately 0.55 to 0.56 units higher. Both models attribute a better maternal education with an increase in the z-score (0.028 units per additional year of schooling). According to both models, boys are more severely affected by stunting than girls and have an average z-score that is 0.21 units lower. It is noteworthy that only the `JSUo_rev` model claims that children born as twins have a much lower z-score compared to that of single birth children (roughly -0.52 units). The `EGB2_rev` model does not indicate any differences between these cases and even claims a positive impact, though it is not statistically significant. The number of total household members does not affect the z-score of children in a meaningful way; for what little influence the models show, it is not significant anyways. The death of one or more children in a family does seem to have a negative influence on the z-score of all remaining children at -0.121 or -0.113 units, respectively, although the p-value of this regressor of both models is only barely statistically insignificant at the $\alpha = 0.05$ level, though it does play a role at a level of $\alpha = 0.1$. The results concerning this regressor are therefore deemed inconclusive.

Urban areas seem to positively affect child development, on average increasing a child's z-score by approximately 0.13 units according to both models. The child's age in months, while statistically significant in the `JSUo_rev` model, does not impact the stunting score in a meaningful way. An increase in the mother's age does have a positive impact, though, at approximately 0.012 units per additional year of age. The 2 models differ in their respective views of the effects of anemia in children and their mothers: the `JSUo_rev` model points towards a negative relationship between childhood anemia and the stunting z-score, though it does not make a connection between maternal anemia and inhibited growth. According to the `EGB2_rev` model, anemia plays no role in determining the average stunting z-score in children.

According to both models, children born to families that already had a large number of children are predicted to have a much reduced z-score compared to first born kids. This effect only shows up when there's 3 or more children born before the current child. Children born earlier in the familial hierarchy are not negatively impacted in a statistically significant way. The number of prenatal visits to a medical professional a mother conducted before giving birth does indicate a quadratic relationship. Taking both regressors together, one can see that, according to both models, 1 or 2 prenatal visits are deemed insufficient, while 3 prenatal visits seem to be the bare minimum (no influence on the z-score). 4 or more visits are predicted to have a positive effect (see Figure A.6 in the Appendix).

In terms of variance the `JSUo_rev` model attributes an increase in the number of siblings aged 5 and under of each child to a greater variance in z-score. The effect

of a child's age on its z-score, though statistically significant, is practically very low. There's some indication that the household region and the loss of 1 or more children increases the variance, but this is only significant at the $\alpha = 0.1$ level. The birth index, while showing large coefficients, is not deemed a significant influence on the variance of the z-scores. There is a large residual variance that resides in the intercept of this model. The `EGB2_rev` model paints a different picture: according to it, there's barely any factors heavily influencing the stunting z-scores, except for the presence of anemia in children which increases the variance by approximately 0.2 units. A slight increase is attributed to each additional child under 5 years of age.

The only thing affecting the distribution of the more extreme quantiles according to the `JSUo_rev` model appears to be the birth order: children born as second or third children to a family are at a higher risk of stunting than firstborn children. The significance of the birth order decreases with an increase of the index, though. This plays no role in the `EGB2_rev` model which attributes only a small effect of the child's age to the kurtosis: as children get older, their risk of falling behind others in terms of body growth increases.

4.4.2 Plausibility Check of the Results and Ultimate Model Selection

Both revised models show plausible results that confirm the findings of the studies cited in Section 3.1. According to both models, wealthier households face a much reduced risk in stunting. This makes sense, as wealthier families have a better access to health care and food and usually live in more sanitary environments (Striessnig and Bora, 2020). The difference between middle income and slightly higher income households, though does not seem to affect the z-scores in a meaningful way; this is most likely due to way the DHS program calculates the household wealth categories. The positive coefficient of the maternal education and the negative coefficient concerning the gender of the child (boys are more severely affected by stunting than girls) also confirm the findings of the aforementioned studies. Interestingly, the `JSUo_rev` model attributes a much lower z-score to twin births while the `EGB2_rev` model does not indicate any effect. The results of the `JSUo_rev` model appear to be more credible, because twin births imply that already limited resources have to be split among 2 children, which causes both children to not be adequately fed. The negative coefficient of the binary variable indicating whether the mother has lost any children is to be expected, too: although not significant at the $\alpha = 0.05$ level, childhood mortality can be attributed to a large number of factors that also affect

and endanger the lives of a mother's other children, such as low sanitary standards, no access to clean water and, as a consequence, prevalence of disease (Gleick, 2002).

Children growing up in urban rather than rural regions generally show higher z-scores. This, too, makes sense as the standard of living in cities is usually higher, as things like electricity and sanitation facilities are easier to provide [p. 13](NISR et al. (2021) find that 86% of all households in urban areas have access to electricity, while only 37% of households in rural areas do). At first glance, the relatively small coefficients of 0.125 in the `JSUo_rev` model and 0.133 in the `EGB2_rev` model seem to indicate only small differences between children growing up in urban and those growing up in rural areas. Morris et al. (2001), however, found that the height-for-age z-scores of children from different neighborhoods within the same city may vary significantly. It is possible that there are quite a large number of both stunted and non-stunted children living in urban areas of Rwanda; differences which the models do not capture, which in turn reduces the coefficients. The minor decrease in the stunting z-score according to the μ and σ parameters of the `JSUo_rev` model indicate that stunting is becoming worse over time (slight decrease in the μ parameter) and that the variability between the individual stunting z-scores decreases, which seems to indicate that once-stunted children have a lower chance of being classified as non-stunted as they grow up (e.g. due to improvements in their environment, such as a better access to health care or more adequate nutrition). The coefficients of these 2 covariates are low, so that effect seems to be very minor compared to all others². Note that the `EGB2_rev` model does not support this thesis (p-values of both the μ and σ coefficients child's age are too high).

The z-scores being dependent on the mother's age makes sense, too. We can infer from the results that children of young mothers are at a higher risk of stunting, which could be due to a number of reasons. For one, inexperience in child care might be a contributing factor (Adedokun and Yaya, 2021). Another reason could be that older mothers have a higher income due to the increase in working experience and subsequent increases in pay. Older mothers may also have a higher education, allowing them to pursue better paying careers which in turn increase the amount of resources that can be devoted to their children. There is some indication according to the `JSUo_rev` model that the prevalence of anemia affects the children's stunting z-score, although this effect is not statistically significant at the $\alpha = 0.05$ level. This goes in line with the prior findings of Mohammed et al. (2019), although the `EGB2_rev` model indicates no connection between anemia and stunting in children.

²Comparing 2 children with a 50 month age difference leads to a decrease in the stunting score of 0.2 units and a decrease in the variance of $\log(0.1)$. Compared to the large intercept value of 1.916, though, it is apparent that the decrease in variance only has a minor effect.

Children born to families with many kids (3 or more children) are much more likely to be affected by stunting than those of smaller families. Again, this is to be expected because of the limited resources that have to be split among the descendants. Children aged 5 and under are especially vulnerable in this regard as shown by Shonkoff et al. (2000) and Victora et al. (2008) (see Section 3.1). A correlation between the increase in the number of children, especially siblings aged 5 and under, and a subsequent decrease in the children’s z-scores, as indicated by both models, is a tenable result. In addition, the increase in the variance of the z-scores with a rising number of children signifies that the individual children’s needs are unevenly accounted for, most likely due to environmental (uneven distribution of resources or higher susceptibility to disease or infection) or parental factors (some children being neglected or improperly taken care of in households that have many children).

The intercept values in the ν parameters of both models, though displaying a differing sign, show that both underlying distributions are slightly right skewed (see Section A.3 in the Appendix). This effect seems to be minor, though, indicated by the fact that the p-value of the intercept in the `JSUo_rev` model is not significant at the $\alpha = 0.05$ level, but that of the intercept in the `EGB2_rev` model, is.

The 2 models attribute changes in the more extreme quantiles of the distributions to different covariates. According to the `JSUo_rev` model, a birth index other than 1 decreases the weight in the more extreme quantiles. The `EGB2_rev` model, however states that an increase in the age of a child has the same effect. This could mean that extreme z-scores are more likely to appear in younger children. The statement of the `JSUo_rev` model is hard to interpret, as the p-values of the categories of the birth order increase with an increase in birth order (pointing towards no significant change). The low p-value might be attributed to a misspecified model in this regard, although neither the worm nor the bucket plot displayed in Figures 4.8a and 4.8b show any indication that this might be the case.

The final model chosen in this analysis is the `JSUo_rev` model. While both models show similar results and point towards similar conclusions, the results of the `JSUo_rev` model are a bit more in line with the prior findings of many studies conducted on the matter of undernutrition and stunting in children. The high p-value of the twin birth coefficient in the `EGB2_rev` model is especially noteworthy, as this seems to contradict prior findings. Whether this is due to numerical instability issues outlined in Section 3.2.2 or other reasons is unclear. The AIC values of both models (10239.35 of the `JSUo_rev` and 10240.49 of the `EGB2_rev` model), too, favor a selection of the `JSUo_rev` over the `EGB2_rev` model. Based on these results, a number of policy recommendations ordered by predicted impact on the stunting z-scores will be made in the upcoming section.

5 Conclusion and Outlook

5.1 Policy Recommendations

The results of this analysis have shown that childhood stunting is a major issue in Rwanda affecting large shares of the population. Given that stunting not only affects a child’s individual height, but is evident of a widespread malnutrition epidemic that severely endangers Rwanda’s economic and humanitarian future, we conclude an assortment of policy measures that should be undertaken to alleviate the impacts of this crisis.

Increase access to education for all Rwandans. Our analysis has shown that higher maternal education correlates with a decrease in the stunting risk of children. Although Rwanda has a compulsory schooling law and grants every Rwandan citizen the constitutional right to education (The Republic of Rwanda, 2003), a large share of the individuals do not even finish the 6 years of elementary school. Only a small percentage of Rwandans from poor households ever attains schools of higher education (NISR et al., 2021, p. 19). This has widespread effects, as an improved education opens up better job prospects, increasing the household wealth and allowing future generations to grow up in environments that allow more resources to be allocated toward its children.

Enhance availability of medical care and clean water access. The results of our analysis show that children whose mothers lost one or more children before are at a higher risk of becoming stunted. The reasons for childhood mortality are manifold (WHO, 2024), but infectious diseases play a key role. Children who survive those infections might suffer from long-term health consequences such as stunting (Prendergast and Humphrey, 2014). The transmission of diseases due to unsafe handling of food has to be curbed. Ensuring clean water access to all parts of the population would allow more children to be given foods free of biological contaminants. In case of sickness, health professionals, such as medical doctors or pediatricians, and appropriate medication need to be readily available in order to stop the worsening of illnesses. Additionally, regular check-ups could alert doctors and parents to afflictions that might negatively impact the development of children

or allow caregivers to receive additional advice related to proper childcare and feeding customs. Young mothers in particular might benefit from that due to their lack of experience in raising children.

Ensure sufficient dietary quantity, quality and diversity for all children. Kids of different ages have different nutritional needs (WHO, 2023). Although this analysis does not take those individual needs into account, the DHS Final Report on Rwanda states that only a small share of children are fed as often and as sufficient as necessary (NISR et al., 2021, p. 180). Diverting resources towards providing complimentary meals in elementary schools might help a significant portion of children to attain their daily nutritional needs which might otherwise not be met. A diverse diet rich in protein might also alleviate the anemia issue that was loosely connected with stunting in this analysis.

Make baby formula accessible to all parts of the population. We have seen that twin births and children with a larger number of siblings are some of the most at-risk groups when it comes to stunting. The splitting of limited nutritional resources among a number of children contributes heavily toward stunting in early life. Making affordable baby formula available to all segments of the population might help combat nutritional deficits, especially among pre-school age children.

In sum, we conclude that Rwanda’s policy measures of recent years and its strive for the “Vision 2050” might lead to prosperity for some, but in the light of widespread human suffering, economic growth is immaterial.

5.2 Limitations of this Thesis and Further Outlook

Possibly one of the most pressing issues of this thesis is the lack of a cluster and stratification adjustment that is necessitated by the complex survey design of the source data outlined in Section 2.1. Current research has paid surprisingly little attention to this topic in connection with GAMLSS. In fact, Stasinopoulos et al. (2024, pp. 239–) present an exemplary GAMLLS application dealing with under-nutrition in India using a survey dataset collected in 2015-16. The authors do not, however, mention the issues arising due to the complex survey design and how to mitigate the effects in their GAMLSS based analysis.

The nutritional needs of children between the ages of 0 and 59 months differ heavily. As described in Section 3.1, this period of a child’s life lays the foundation for its future life. Research has shown that this age group may be split into 3 different types, namely those between the ages of 0 and 5 months, 6 and 23 months

and between 24 and 59 months. While infants (0 to 5 months) are recommended to be exclusively breastfed, children between the ages of 6 and 23 months are to be given complementary solid foods in addition to mother’s milk. Children above this age are to be weaned off breast milk as parents see fit (WHO, 2023). A more complex analysis of the determinants of malnutrition in children should therefore take the individual nutritional needs of these 3 age groups into account. As stated in the Final Report accompanying the dataset, only 22% of children between the ages of 6 and 23 months had their nutritional requirements met (see Section 2.3). The dataset contains additional data on the feeding practices of the individual children’s mothers; a binary variable indicating the sufficient feeding of every child could therefore be constructed and incorporated into the analysis.

Except for the $(M14)^2$ regressor (describing the number of prenatal care visits squared) polynomial and interaction terms were not examined in this analysis. Such additional terms may hint towards an unaccounted interplay between the different factors that might expose additional relationships and yield further insights into the matter at hand.

In order to guarantee a reasonable predictive quality of the model, cross validation could be incorporated into the analysis workflow. The `gamlss` package in R contains the function `gamlssCV()` which performs a k -fold cross validation on a GAMLSS model. A k -fold cross validation in particular splits the dataset into k subsets (“folds”) of equal size. The GAMLSS model is calculated based on $k - 1$ subsets and validated on the remaining set. This process is repeated k times, whereby the subset used to validate the model is changed in every iteration. The results of the runs are then averaged and a final GAMLSS model is obtained. This method, however, is computationally expensive as the model has to be re-calculated k times and lies outside of the scope of this thesis.

The `gamboostLSS` package in R implements the *gamboostLSS* algorithm first introduced by Mayr et al. (2012). It replaces the Gauss-Newton optimization with a gradient boosting technique that allows for both model fitting and variable selection. The drawbacks of AIC-based variable and model selection techniques used in Section 4.3, often noted to be “unstable” (Hofner et al., 2014, p. 2), can be mitigated this way which leads to better fitting models, especially those with multiple distribution parameters (such as the 4-parameter EGB2 and JSUo models developed in this thesis).

An implementation of these techniques and adjustments will most likely lead to better and more precise estimates than those of our final JSUo_rev model. This, however, may be the subject of future research.

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A Appendix

A.1 2006 WHO Reference Growth Curves

The following 2 figures are the 2006 WHO Reference Growth Curves for boys of different ages. The growth curves for girls are similar, but less steep. At the age of 60 months, the growth curve values are almost identical (see Figure A.3).

Figure A.1: 2006 WHO Length-for-Age Reference Growth Curve for boys aged 0 to 24 months. The green line represents the median length-for-age values, the other lines show the number of standard deviations from the median line. Source: WHO, 2006, p. 33

Figure A.2: 2006 WHO Length-for-Age Reference Growth Curve for boys aged 24 to 60 months. The green line represents the median length-for-age values, the other lines show the number of standard deviations from the median line. Source: WHO, 2006, p. 34

Figure A.3: Comparison of the 2006 WHO Length-for-Age Reference Growth Curve for boys and girls aged 0 to 60 months. The green lines represent the median length-for-age values (solid for boys, dashed-dotted for girls), the other lines show the number of standard deviations from the median line. Source: WHO, 2006, p. 75

A.2 Summary of the NO_3step Model After 3-Step Variable Selection

Mu coefficients	Category	Estimate	P-value
(Intercept)		-1.528	< 0.0001
Household wealth quintile (compared to "Middle")	Poorest	-0.335	< 0.0001
	Poor	-0.217	< 0.0001
	Richer	0.097	0.0919
	Richest	0.585	< 0.0001
Maternal education (years)		0.033	< 0.0001
Gender of child	Male	-0.208	< 0.0001
Prenatal visits squared		0.024	0.0031
Twin birth	Yes	-0.528	< 0.0001
No. of household members		-0.024	0.0435
Child's age (months)		-0.004	0.0009
Mother had children die	Yes	-0.146	0.0092
Household region	Urban	0.125	0.0240
Mother's age (years)		0.006	0.0544
Child is anemic	Yes	-0.083	0.1203
No. of siblings 5 and under		-0.066	0.0510
Prenatal visits		-0.076	0.0445
Sigma coefficients		Estimate	P-value
(Intercept)		0.013	0.7770
Birth order	2 or 3	-0.026	0.4202
	4 or 5	0.026	0.5026
	6+	0.105	0.0250
Child's age (months)		-0.002	0.0083
No. of siblings 5 and under		0.040	0.0201
Maternal education (years)		0.008	0.0132
Mother had children die	Yes	0.068	0.0760
Child is anemic	Yes	0.058	0.0924

Table A.1: Output of the `summary()` command in R of the `NO_3step` model after performing the 3-step variable selection procedure outlined in Section 4.3.

A.3 Plots of the JSU₀ and EGB2 Distributions Using Different Parameter Settings

For more details see Rigby et al. (2019, pp. 385–387, pp. 389–391).

Figure A.4: Sample density curves of Johnson’s S_u distribution function $\text{JSU}_0(\mu, \sigma, \nu, \tau)$ with $\mu = 0$, $\sigma = 1$, $\nu \in \{0, -1, -2\}$ and $\tau \in \{1, 2, 3\}$. The distribution is symmetric if $\nu = 0$. A mirroring of the distribution along the Y axis can be achieved by setting ν to $-\nu$.

Figure A.5: Sample density curves of the exponential generalized beta type 2 distribution function $\text{EGB2}(\mu, \sigma, \nu, \tau)$ with $\mu = 0$, $\sigma = 1$, $\nu \in \{1, 2, 5\}$ and $\tau \in \{1, 2, 5\}$. The distribution is symmetric if $\nu = \tau$. A mirroring of the distribution along the Y axis around the mean μ can be achieved by swapping the ν and τ parameters.

A.4 List of Distribution Abbreviations

The `chooseDist()` command in Section 4.2 yielded an output of GAIC values of a number of different distributions, the names of which were abbreviated according to the R output. The following table lists the names and the number of parameters of each distribution in the order given in Table 4.1.

Model	Underlying distribution	No. of parameters
ST5	Skew t type 5	4
TF2	T family type 2 distribution	3
SST	Skew Student t	4
SN1	Skew normal type 1 distribution	3
SEP2	Skew exponential power type 2 distribution	4
ST2	Skew t type 2	4
SEP1	Skew exponential power type 1 distribution	4
GT	Generalized t distribution	4
TF	t family distribution	3
ST4	Skew t type 4	4
PE2	Power exponential type 2 distribution	3
PE	Power exponential family distribution	3
ST3	Skew t type 3	4
SEP4	Skew exponential power type 4 distribution	4
SEP3	Skew exponential power type 3 distribution	4
SN2	Skew normal type 2 distribution	3
SHASH	Sinh-arcsinh distribution	4
SHASHo2	Second parameterization of the SHASHo distribution	4
LO	Logistic distribution	2
SHASHo	Original Sinh-arcsinh distribution	4
NET	Normal-exponential- t distribution	2
RG	Reverse Gumbel / Type I Extreme Value Distribution	2
GU	Gumbel Distribution	2
JSU	Reparameterized Johnson's S_u distribution	4

Table A.2: List of the underlying distributions of the models examined in Section 4.2. The number of parameters is shown that characterizes each distribution. Distributions with 2 parameters include the μ and σ parameters, those with 3 also contain the ν (skewness) and those with 4 also include the τ (kurtosis) parameter.

For details concerning the properties these distributions and where they originate from, see Rigby et al. (2019, pp. 365–).

A.4.1 Effect of Prenatal Visits on Stunting Z-Score According to the JSUo_rev and EGB2_rev Models

Figure A.6: Effect of the number of prenatal visits on the stunting z-score according to the JSUo_rev and EGB2_rev models. The curves of both models are almost identical, so only 1 curve (using the coefficients of the JSUo_rev model is shown. Both models indicate that 4 or more prenatal visits result in a positive effect on the stunting z-score.

Versicherung

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Bielefeld, den 15.08.2024

Dennis Meurer

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